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[PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES FOR DEVELOPING HIGHER-ORDER THINKING: ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVE]

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Abstract

To equip the students of elementary education to face the challenges of the 21st century, the importance of higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) is undeniable, so that learners are expected to leave memorization and shift to using authentic analysis, evaluation and creation. This study aimed to explore the teachers' views on pedagogical practices and instructional approaches being adopted by the elementary school teachers for the development of HOTS in government schools of Sialkot. To better understand teachers' lived experiences of planning, teaching, questioning and assessing for higher-order thinking, a qualitative approach of a phenomenological research design was used in an interpretative paradigm. The elementary teachers, as the information-rich cases were purposively chosen and semi-structured interviews using a self-developed interview guide regarding Bloom's revised taxonomy and current HOTS literature were carried out. With consent, interviews were audio-recorded and then transcribed in their entirety, anonymised and analysed using reflexive thematic analysis in line with the six steps outlined by Braun and Clarke. The one main theme that emerged was "Instructional methods and pedagogical practices for developing HOTS" with five sub-themes; Questioning techniques as HOTS catalysts, collaborative and group-based learning, activity-based, hands-on, and project-based learning, HOTS-oriented lesson planning and assessment practices and HOTS. It is found that some teachers intentionally intend to instigate analysis, comparison, justification, and problem solving through open-ended questioning ("how", "why", "what if"), group discussion, role play, real-life tasks, and practical activity and some teachers purposefully intend formal and informal assessment involving HOTS objectives in the lesson plan. Meanwhile, participants identified important structural barriers, such as big classes, lack of resources, testing-led assessment, and low professional training levels, that result in an ongoing "practical gap" between their beliefs about HOTS and their real-time classroom options. Elementary educators acknowledge the value and make some efforts to cultivate HOTS, but systemic support, targeted professional learning, and assessment redesign are needed to support and expand HOTS-based pedagogy.

Keywords: Teaching methods, Critical Thinking, pedagogical practice, Instructional Strategies, Cognitive development

Introduction

Higher-order thinking skills are processes that are developed in the mind beyond memory and understanding that involve using, analysing, evaluating and creating knowledge. HOTS are mental operations that include critical thinking, transfer and problem solving, which allow the learner to interpret and make reasoned judgments about information presented to them, which encourages them to come up with new ideas (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001; Brookhart, 2010). In general, understanding and recall abilities are considered as lower-order skills, while the HOTS skills require students to explore relationships, make inferences, support their standpoints, and synthesize the ideas in new situations. Teachers whose instruction focuses on reasoning, investigation, and problem-solving foster more confident students who can flexibly apply their learning to different situations and contexts (Eisenman & Payne, 2016).

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In the 21st century, the importance of teaching and learning their students' critical, creative and analytical skills has been taken up more in the education system rather than mere memorisation. Analysis, evaluation, and creation have been identified as some of the higher levels of thinking (HOTS) that are essential for students to prepare them to solve real-world problems, engage in knowledge economies, and become informed decision makers (Conklin, 2011; Dwyer et al., 2014). But, in many elementary schools, the old styles of lecturing and reciting still dominate as the coverage of the curriculum and exam results take precedence over understanding and inquiry. The pedagogical strategies used by teachers thus play the critical role of building up either the capacity to remember or the capacity to think critically to generate innovations and alternatives while responding to classroom challenges or life challenges (Podina et al., 2020; Saido et al., 2017).

Studies and policy documents of today's era in Pakistan have indicated the increasing concern for reducing the student's cognitive development in the adoption of only rote memorizing and book-oriented learning. The classrooms that take priority over conceptual understanding, analytical work, and questioning and do so to finish the syllabus and pass high-stakes exams, have been the focus of attention in national assessment reports and reform efforts. An attempt to change this trend with a goal of encouraging problem solving, reasoning, and practical skills among learners is in the process of being translated from national policy to classroom practice under the umbrella of Bloom's taxonomy. To find a direction for realistic, context-sensitive reform, it is important to understand how the elementary teachers themselves conceptualise and try to develop HOTS.

Every transformation to HOTS-oriented pedagogy is mediated by teacher beliefs, planning and classroom practices, which form the central pivot in such transformation. Past research indicated that primary teachers are aware of the values of HOTS, as well as its relevance to 21st century skills, but they complain of challenges regarding resources, teacher training, and assessment system (Hassan et al., 2018; Zohar & Cohen, 2016; Yee et al., 2015). Higher-order and critical thinking skills have been emphasized in the current literature (Jamil et al., 2025; Naseer et al., 2022). Based on international and regional explorations of the concepts of 'active learning' or teaching by inquiry or questioning approach, it is suggested that such learning approaches as problem-based learning, task-based learning, and higher-order learning approach could contribute to developing reasoning and transfer of knowledge in students (Heung et al., 2011; Saido et al., 2017; Carrillo et al., 2025). In this context, the current study aims to explore the pedagogical practices and instructional strategies that elementary teachers in Sialkot identify as conducive to the promotion of HOTS and how teachers overcome the tension between their aspirations and structures.

Research Objective

- To explore the pedagogical practices used by elementary school teachers to develop higher-order thinking skills among students.

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Research Question

- What pedagogical practices do elementary school teachers use to develop higher-order thinking skills among elementary students?

Literature Review

There is a close interaction between HOTS and the educational reform that is related to Bloom's taxonomy, which categorises educational cognitive processes by levels. The levels that interact with each other, lower-order cognitive levels are remembering and understanding, higher-order cognitive levels are applying, analysing, evaluating, and creating. HOTS are the higher orders of this taxonomy where the learners engage in application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation using the knowledge they acquire to develop metacognitive awareness and the knowledge of "thinking about thinking." Contemporary perspectives on learning focus on learning not being fixed but socially and culturally constructed, and students' ability to transfer what they learned in classrooms to real-world environments (Gipps & Stobart, 2003), as focused on in the current literature (Jamil et al., 2024). In the context of science education, for instance, it is not just about remembering facts but also learning and thinking about working like a scientist, carrying out investigations, interpreting data, and making justifiable inferences (Khethail, 2019; Kusumastuti et al., 2021).

There is considerable research linking HOTS development with active/inquiry-based pedagogy. According to Heung et al., HOTS is an effort of the students to think broadly about new problems in an innovative and flexible way, while Zohar and Cohen stress that the conventional approach, which is lecture-based, tends to narrow down students' thinking in terms of recall and replication processes. The questioning strategies, especially open-ended and Socratic questioning, have been recognized as an effective approach to involve higher-order thinking skills because of their ability to prompt students for further exploration, justification, and evaluation of their thinking (Etemadzadeh et al., 2013; Paul & Elder, 2006). Likewise, problem-solving and real-world enquiry methods encourage the students to formulate problems, to engage in creative thinking, to find answers to their problems, and to test their solutions by investigation, and so develop the ability to think creatively and critically, and to be curious. Recently, work on practical and problem-solving approaches in science and other subjects has been proven to promote the reasoning, analysis, and transfer skills of the students (Saido et al. al, 2017; Siddique and Rana, 2021).

Active learning is also practically implemented using active learning frameworks, which further emphasize the importance of students in HOTS development through meaningful learning tasks. Instead, Carrillo et al. (2025) emphasize the potential of activities that engage students with peers to collaborate, discuss, and reflect to increase their analytical and problem-solving abilities. International research has been reported where teachers who implemented active learning methods noted positive changes in students' ability to express their ideas, challenge their assumptions, and relate the new knowledge to what they have experienced (Asterhan et al., 2015; Lee & Lai, 2017). However, studies reveal ongoing challenges, such as time constraints, overloaded

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curricula, and classroom management issues, all of which can hinder teachers from consistently incorporating HOTS-supportive practices (Carrillo et al., 2025; Novita et al., 2023; Azid et al., 2022).

In the case of Pakistan and generally elsewhere, promoting the development of HOTS in many instances is a policy priority, but there is a disconnection between classroom truths and instructions from the needs and aspirations of the policymakers. Several researchers have highlighted the necessity for teacher professional development to prepare teachers in creating questions, tasks, and assessments for HOTS because many teachers had difficulties in formulating questions of high level and failed to incorporate HOTS in their teaching practice (Novita et al., 2023; Azid et al., 2022; Siddique & Rana, 2021). Research suggests that teachers also need the support of institutions and a collaborative school culture to facilitate classroom and assessment issues related to the teaching of HOTS (Noone & Hogan, 2018b; Yee et al., 2015). However, there is little in-depth research to find out how Pakistani government school elementary teachers perceive the HOTS and how they explain their approach and limitations in teaching HOTS and thus this study aimed to find out the answers to these questions.

Research Methodology

This is a qualitative study in which the paradigm used is interpretivist with a phenomenological research design, where it is carried out by looking at how the teachers' perception and practice in the elementary classroom affect the development of HOTS. Phenomenology research design was appropriate because the purpose of this study is to understand teachers' lived experience, teachers' classroom practices and teachers' meanings attached to HOTS and not to measure predefined variables (Creswell & Poth, 2016). To achieve the aim of the study, 12 teachers at government schools were selected as information-rich cases who had experience teaching at the elementary level using purposive sampling (Etikan et al., 2016; Guest et al., 2006). Qualitative data was generated with the use of semi-structured interviews with an interview schedule created based on the literature. With the use of semi-structured interviews, the participants described their questioning practice, their approach to group work, activity-based learning, assessment practice and lesson planning in detail. Informed consent was obtained and interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, anonymised and checked for accuracy. Patterns and themes were discovered using Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022), which consisted of familiarisation, coding, theme development, review, definition and reporting iterations, including focus on reflexive engagement by the researchers. Questions of ethics (voluntary participation, confidentiality, informed consent and respect for the working dignity of the participants in their profession) were meticulously observed.

Findings of the Study

Based on the data from the students, the following theme emerged.

Instructional Method and Pedagogical Practice for Developing HOTS

This theme looks at the pedagogical aspect of the participants' work, including the classroom experience they facilitated, the activities they created, and the specific strategies they used to activate and develop HOTS. Five sub-themes were identified: (10

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Questioning strategies as HOTS catalysts, (2) Group-based learning, (3) Hands-on, activity-based, and project-based learning. (4) Assessments aligned with HOTS. (5) HOTS-oriented lesson planning.

1.1

1.2 Sub-Theme 1: Questioning Techniques as HOTS Catalysts

Questioning was the most well-respected and popular method of causing HOTS among the twelve participants. The teacher explained a deliberate shift away from closed, recall-based questions, which asked students to repeat what they had learned, to open-ended questions that ask students to explain, compare, justify, evaluate, and predict. Several participants reported that "how", "what", and "why" questions were particularly effective in transforming students from passive recipients into active intellectual agents.

Participant 6 described her experience in the following way:

Students are encouraged to think critically when a question is asked in class and respond by asking follow-up questions like; why", " how," what", and "if". These strategies stimulate their curiosity, promote critical thinking, and help them investigate the subject from several perspectives. Student improve their reasoning skills and memory by answering these kinds of questions regularly.

From the viewpoint of participant 11, it was stated as:

I am more friendly with them. I take more than one answer from them. I take opinions from everyone so that the students can express their thoughts and give arguments. For example, if there are 20 students in my classroom and I ask one of them a question, and if all 20 students answer, then I will have 20 different answers. Accordingly, for one question, I will have 20 answers, which contain the students' different perspectives, knowledge, and material for deeper thinking. This itself becomes material for deeper thinking within the class.

Participant 10 conveyed her thoughts in the following words:

When we ask different questions to students, they give different answers according to their views and ideas. In addition, in group discussions, such questions help students to think, analyze, and develop the ability to solve problems. The question is not the end point of learning; it is the beginning of a genuine intellectual journey.

According to participant 2, it was articulated as follows:

For example, if the question is asked: how, why, and if — this deepens the children's thinking. Simple recall questions keep the student at the surface level. But when you ask them why something happened, or what would happen if something were different, you force them to go inside the topic, to reason, to imagine, to analyze. That is when higher-order thinking truly begins.

Participant 7 presented her views in the following words:

During the lesson, we first ask students different types of questions related to the topic so that they start thinking and become involved in the learning process. These questions help students express their ideas and understand the lesson more deeply. I design questions that require students to analyze, explain, and give their opinions rather than simply reproduce what the textbook has stated.

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1.3 Sub-Theme 2: Collaborative and Group-Based Learning

Group discussion and collaborative learning were described by the majority of participants as among the most effective and most frequently used strategies for developing HOTS. Students were divided into small groups so they could discuss the topic, evaluate different points of view, look at the problem, and share a common understanding. When compared to individual or whole-class instructions, the social dynamic of group interaction was found to produce more confident thinking: students offered alternative perspectives and challenged each other's ideas. Role-play and dramatization were also described by several participants as powerful collaborative vehicles for developing analytical and evaluative thinking.

In the perspective of participant 5, it was stated as follows:

At the elementary level, we take higher-order thinking, in which children do analysis, comparison, and share their problems, and then we find out the solution together. When students sit together in a group and analyze a question or a situation, they bring different experiences and perspectives. The group becomes a community of inquiry in which thinking is shared, tested, and refined through dialogue.

Participant 4 described her opinion in these words:

In our syllabus, there is a topic about health and cleanliness. We made the children read a drama text, do questions and answers, and do book exercises. But we did not leave the drama only up to the book. We made the children play a small dramatic performance and made them take on the characters. This activity required them to understand the characters' perspectives and motivations at a deeper level.

In the words of participant 9, it was explained as follows:

The student participated in the group discussion and presented different ideas. In their discussion, there was a lot of experience and thought. They criticized each other's ideas and saw the different aspects of the topic with deep thought. The discussion then moved into the full class, where different ideas were compared and evaluated. This is how collaborative inquiry develops genuine higher-order thinking in elementary students.

Participant 6 provided her viewpoint in the following words:

In our opinion, it should be storytelling and role-playing characters. Other than that, it should be co-curricular activities and projects through which children can actively participate. When children take on a character in a story or a role in a dramatization, they must think about motivation, consequence, and perspective — all of which are core dimensions of higher-order analytical thinking.

1.4 Sub-Theme 3: Activity-Based, Hands-On, and Project-Based Learning

Activity-based and hands-on approaches were consistently valued by participants for their capacity to engage elementary students both intellectually and physically, making HOTS accessible to learners who might disengage from purely verbal or text-based instruction. Participants described using real-world experiments, community problem-solving projects, first-aid demonstrations, science investigations, creative writing tasks, and computer lab activities as vehicles for HOTS development. Several participants noted that when students were required to engage practically with a concept — rather than read about it — their intellectual engagement deepened and their capacity for analysis

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and reasoning was visibly activated. Real-life contextualization was a consistent feature of these approaches: participants connected lesson content to students' lived environments to make HOTS meaningful and applicable.

According to the account of participant 9, it was stated as:

Absolutely. In the first aid training, we taught the students how to perform first aid. When a child was injured at school, the same topic was in the book. We taught the children how to relate their syllabus to the real situation and how to utilize their knowledge practically. The connection between book knowledge and real-life application is precisely where higher-order thinking is activated and developed.

Participant 10 elaborated her thoughts in the following way:

I did a research activity in Pakistan on a local issue, in which the students were asked to debate on the reasons and solutions for poverty in their locality. This gives the children a real problem to engage with and gives them the ability to think beyond the classroom. It requires them to analyze causes, evaluate potential solutions, and argue for a position — all classic HOTS operations.

In the view of participant 8, it was described as follows:

We made the students do a live practical. As trainers, we called in professionals from the health department and introduced their work to the students. Apart from that, if there is an art or a life topic that can be made practical, we get the children to do it as a live practical activity.

1.5 Sub-Theme 4: HOTS-Oriented Lesson Planning

According to the participants, lesson planning was a crucial area where HOTS intentions were converted into pedagogical action. In contrast to the traditional pattern of content-first planning, some participants described a purposeful planning process that prioritized the identification of higher-order learning objectives over the choice of questioning technique and activities. Creating open-ended questions, real-world examples, group activities, activating previous knowledge, and reflection were all crucial planning components.

Participant 1 conveyed her perspective in these words:

Yes, when we make a lesson plan, we make sure that the questions are such that they reveal students' creativity and analytical skills. We include group-based discussions and project-based activities. Planning is where the HOTS work really begins — if you do not build in the space for deeper thinking at the planning stage, it rarely happens spontaneously in the lesson itself.

Participant 7 expressed her understanding in the following words:

First, I clearly define the learning objectives and try to include tasks that require students to think deeply about the topic. I design questions that encourage students to explain their ideas, give reasons for their answers, and connect new knowledge with their previous knowledge. The lesson plan is a map that ensures every stage of the lesson has a genuine higher-order thinking component embedded within it.

In the opinion of participant 11, it was narrated as follows:

I ask practical questions, set up group discussions, and give students projects to take home so that they can go home, apply their minds to a problem, and present different solutions in

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the following lesson. In order to deepen my students' thinking further, I also prepare different visual materials and observational tasks for them.

According to participant 6, it was explained in these words:

We actively encourage student to participate in hands-on activities by actively incorporating their question into the lesson plan. This method allows students to be actively engaged in the learning process, apply concepts to real-world situations, and gain a deeper understanding of the subject. We make the lesson more engaging and intellectually challenging by involving students in practical tasks and interactive exercises.

1.6 Sub-Theme 5: Assessment Practices and HOTS

Several participants described formative or informal assessment practices as a useful tool for both cultivating and identifying higher-order thinking, while the prevalent formal assessment system, which is based on a written exam that primarily rewards recall, was widely acknowledged as a structural barrier to HOTS. The participants' reflection on the relationship between assessments and HOTS development revealed a constructive tension. The teacher used a range of informal strategies, such as classroom discussion, oral questioning technique, group observation, and feedback cycle, to assess their students' thinking level and adjust their instructions accordingly.

Participant 3 reflected her ideas in the following:

Assessments serve as a continuous process that encourages students to do more than just memorize facts; they also encourage them to evaluate and analyze them. Regular assessments, both formal and informal, help students develop critical thinking and apply concepts in a variety of contexts.

In the words of participant 6, it was presented as follows:

My instructions on higher-order thinking skills are greatly influenced by assessment techniques. When assessments require reasoning, analysis, and problem-solving, I try to plan my lesson so that students are motivated to think critically rather than just memorize facts. This encourages me to use teaching strategies like questioning and discussion rather than the strictly content-transmission method.

Participant 5 shared her insights in the following words:

Assessment helps me identify a student's areas of weakness. I inform the student about the area of difficulty. I can more precisely target my activities and questions to fill in the gaps when I know which students are struggling with evaluation or analysis.

Discussion

The findings of the study show that the understanding of HOTS in the minds of the elementary teachers in this study is quite good, and the efforts made by elementary teachers in applying all the instructional models in this study are active efforts to make questioning, working hands-on, and purposeful planning to stimulate students to think and analyze in the classroom, which can be seen in problem solving. The way they purposefully progressed from closed recall to the open-ended "how", "why," and "what if" questions aligns with literature that suggests that questioning sets the depth of student thinking (Paul & Elder, 2006; Etemadzadeh et al., 2013; Zohar & Cohen, 2016). What is observed in the use of group discussions, role-play, drama, and project-based tasks (Asterhan et al., 2015; Carrillo et al., 2025; Saido et al., 2017) demonstrates that a

cooperative and active learning approach can provide a classroom community of inquiry where students test, refine and extend their ideas. Their focus on real-life applications, such as first-aid training and implementing their local social issues, is in line with Deweyan concepts of experiential learning and research that living contexts link the content to students' socio-cultures, which is essential for achieving meaningful HOTS learning (Dewey, 1930; Gipps & Stobart, 2003; Lee & Lai, 2017; Siddique & Rana, 2021). At the same time, teachers reported that there was tension between informal assessment to support HOTS and formal exams for recall, which confirms previous efforts (Noone & Hogan, 2018b) that this tension can be seen between the ideals and reality of HOTS in the classroom and requires targeted training and institutional support to narrow the "practical gap" (Yee et al., 2015; Azid et al., 2022; Novita et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Elementary school teachers in Sialkot know the importance of HOTS for better preparedness of students in cognitive as well as life skills and use various pedagogical strategies like activity-based/post activity-based learning, project-based learning, real-life applications, as well as using open-ended questioning and lesson planning techniques to develop HOTS in students; the study concludes that these teachers use these pedagogical strategies to develop and nurture HOTS in learners. Teachers also employ formative assessment (observation, verbal questioning, verbal feedback) to monitor and enhance students' higher-order thinking, although they recognise that the preponderance of the formal examination systems is recall-oriented. Further, ineffective utilization of HOTS pedagogy is constrained by structural barriers, such as large class sizes, limited resources and space, curriculum pressure and lack of sustained professional development. Therefore, strengthening HOTS at the elementary level will require coordinated action at a number of levels: first, at a school level, the leadership of the school has to value and protect time for active learning; second, at a professional development level, professional development has to be an activity that targets the planning, questioning and evaluating, and creativity of HOTS; third, at a policy level, policy and assessment of the education system should reward analysis, evaluation and creativity, not only rote reproduction.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this research, the following are some recommendations:

1. Deliver and implement ongoing, practice-based professional learning for elementary teachers centered on HOTS-focused questioning, group facilitation and activity-based learning, and give teachers chances for co-creating, testing, and modifying HOTS lessons together.
2. Help school leaders to become instructional leaders who make HOTS explicit by spending time in classrooms, providing feedback and recognition for classroom practices that involve higher-order tasks, and providing feedback and recognition to teachers for how they are integrating higher-order tasks into their everyday teaching.
3. Create time for systematic collaboration, including co-developing lesson plans with HOTS in mind, exchange of successful implementation and activities, and review meetings after teaching as a way to discuss challenges.

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4. Ensure that the level of the assessments built in classrooms is aligned with HOTS practices; school-level tests will include higher-order questions, open-ended tasks, and/or performance-based assessments; teachers will be provided with guidance and marking support to ensure they feel confident in evaluating and scoring students' analytical and creative responses.
5. Promote changes in structure by calling for smaller classes, greater availability of simple tools and more flexible classroom design, and a classroom environment that doesn't stifle students' questions, debates, and the taking of intellectual risks.

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